

Determination of Soluble Sulphide in Presence of Interfering Ions by Complexometric Method

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In recent years photochemical hydrogen evolution reactions has been performed using semiconductor photocatalysts in presence of sulphide and sulphite mixture¹. For the study of kinetics of such processes, determination of sulphide in presence of sulphite and/or thiosulphate is necessary.

In our studies on photocatalytic decomposition of sulphide using mixed semiconductor systems, we got interested in the determination of sulphide in solution containing sulphite and thiosulphate². The determination of sulphide by conventional methods, (i) iodimetry based on the reaction, $\text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{I}_2 = 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{I}^- + \text{S}$, and (ii) quantitative precipitation of arsenic(III) sulphide followed by iodimetric estimation of excess arsenic(III) are known³. For the estimation of sulphide in the sodium sulphide prepared for our work we used eudiometric method by liberating H_2S from the sulphide solution on acidification and then measuring the volume. There is no reference of this method in literature. None of these methods, however, can be used to determine sulphide in presence of sulphite and/or thiosulphate. Amongst other methods, the cadmium complex of EDTA has been used to estimate the sulphide⁴. Based on the reaction $\text{CdY}^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{S} = \text{CdS} + \text{H}_2\text{Y}^{2-}$, the liberated EDTA (H_2Y^{2-}) is estimated with calcium. For the quantitative liberation of EDTA the solution has to be boiled for 15 min and filtered; the accuracy achieved is around 1%. This study did not evaluate the interference by other ions. Of the other methods reported, sulphide sensitive electrodes⁵ has been used for potentiometric titration of sulphides with Pb^{II} ; the deviation is ± 0.5 to $\pm 2\%$. Titration of sulphides in natural water has

been reported using mercuric chloride⁶. Recently trace amounts of S^{2-} have been estimated by converting the liberated H_2S to thiocyanate which is determined spectrophotometrically (upper-limit $6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)⁷

Here we report an accurate method for the rapid determination of sulphide in presence of sulphite and/or thiosulphate and other interfering ions, by adding standard cadmium solution directly to the sulphide solution and estimating the excess Cd^{2+} with standard EDTA solution.

Results and Discussion

Estimation of sulphide by complexometric method (Table 1) compares well with that by standard sodium arsenite method³. Table 2 shows that if the acidity is not adjusted properly around 0.1 N HCl the results are too high. During precipitation of cadmium sulphide by addition of Cd^{2+} ions to the sodium sulphide solution (which has high pH), cadmium hydroxide is also formed. But when this mixture is acidified with HCl and warmed, the oxide dissolves, giving reproducible results. The complexometric method for determination of sulphide was repeated in presence of a number of anions, viz. sulphite, thiosulphate, nitrate, chloride, iodide, formate, oxalate etc. and cations, viz. Na^+ , K^+ etc. for their possible interference. The results are presented in Table 3.

The present procedure is simpler. The only precaution to be taken is to adjust the acidity after addition of CdCl_2 solution. The accuracy of the present method is better. The quantitative estimation of sulphide in presence of sulphite and/or thiosulphate

can not be done by the standard sodium arsenite or eudiometric method. This complexometric method has the merit of overcoming the difficulty. The determination is accurate and rapid in comparison to the conventional method³.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SULPHIDE BY COMPLEXOMETRIC METHOD

Amount of sulphide* taken (mg)	Amount of sulphide** found (mg)	Standard deviation (mg) $n = 5$
6.15	6.18	0.02
12.30	12.36	0.03
24.58	24.45	0.05
36.87	36.87	0.08
49.16	49.26	0.10
61.46	61.63	0.13
122.91	123.23	0.16

* Determined by Na₃AsO₃ method. ** Mean of five determinations. $n =$ Number of determinations.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF SULPHIDE BY COMPLEXOMETRIC METHOD AT VARIOUS ACID CONCENTRATIONS*

Sulphide taken = 12.29 mg

Concn. of HCl (N)	Amount of sulphide found (mg)	Standard deviation (mg) $n = 5$
0.00	14.11	0.40
0.01	13.76	0.09
0.1	12.33	0.03

Determined by Na₃AsO₃ method. $n =$ Mean of five determinations \pm standard deviation.

Experimental

Cadmium chloride (Thomas Morson), ethylene-diamine tetraacetic acid (Glaxo), sodium thiosulphate (E. Merck), iodine (Glaxo), sodium arsenite (Merck) and erichrome black T (Merck) were used as such. All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Cadium(II) solution was prepared by dissolving cadmium chloride (A.R.) in 0.1 N acetic acid and standardised against standard EDTA solution⁸. Solutions of EDTA (0.01 mol dm⁻³), sodium thiosulphate, iodine (0.2 mol dm⁻³) and sodium arsenite (0.05 mol dm⁻³), were prepared using double-distilled water and standardised³. Ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer solution (pH 10) was prepared according to the reported procedure³. A 0.4% erichrome black T solution in methanol was prepared. Sodium sul-

phide solution was prepared by passing H₂S through sodium hydroxide solution (1 mol dm⁻³) in N₂-atmosphere under magnetically stirred condition.

TABLE 3—COMPLEXOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF SULPHIDE IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Ion	Amount of ion taken mg	Amount of sulphide taken mg	Amount of sulphide found mg
-	-	122.91	123.26
-	-	307.28	308.61
SO ₃ ²⁻	307.28	122.91	123.90
-	768.2	307.28	309.60
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	430.19	122.91	124.51
-	1075.48	307.28	311.28
SO ₄ ²⁻	368.74	122.91	123.76
-	921.84	307.28	309.52
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ /SO ₃ ²⁻ /SO ₄ ²⁻	307.28/430.19/368.74	122.91	123.97
-	368.2/1075.48/921.84	307.28	310.30
Cl ⁻	272.71	122.91	123.23
-	681.78	307.28	308.16
NO ₃ ⁻	238.14	122.91	123.20
-	295.36	307.28	308.00
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	338.01	122.91	124.16
-	845.02	307.28	310.24
CH ₃ COO ⁻	226.62	122.91	123.776
-	556.56	307.28	309.28
HCOO ⁻	172.85	122.91	123.71
-	432.11	307.28	309.44
Br ⁻	307.28	122.91	123.96
-	768.2	307.28	308.32
I ⁻	487.80	122.91	123.32
-	1291.51	307.28	308.48
Na ⁺	88.34	122.91	123.23
-	220.85	307.28	308.16
K ⁺	149.70	122.91	123.26
-	374.49	307.28	308.10
NH ₄ ⁺	69.138	122.91	123.29
-	172.85	307.28	308.08

Determination of sulphide by complexometric method : The sodium sulphide solution (10 ml) was diluted to 125 ml and to it 1 M cadmium(II) solution (5 ml) was added. The solution was then acidified with 0.2 N HCl to keep the acidity at 0.1 N. The mixture was warmed at 60–70° and the volume made up to 250 ml and allowed to settle for 5–10 min. An aliquot (25 ml) of supernatant solution was titrated against standard EDTA solution in ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (pH 10) using eriochrome black T as indicator to the blue end-point. The concentration of sodium sulphide was calculated after performing proper blank titration.

NOTE

Depending on the concentration of sulphide, appropriate volume of the solution was taken and diluted accordingly.

For comparison sulphide solution was standardised by sodium arsenite method³.

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